

Basic features for Msc thesis on GR

We want to generate a test notebook with basic features used in Mathematica and RGCT package:
<https://faculty.washington.edu/lgy/ph564/> (working link)

Simple computations and time performances of RGCT

`AbsoluteTiming[expr]` evaluates `expr`, returning a list of the absolute number of seconds in real time that have elapsed, together with the result obtained.

Analysis

```
In[1]:= (* A good first step is always to clear  
all the variables in order to start from scratch*)  
ClearAll["Global`*"]
```

```
In[2]:= timing = AbsoluteTime[];
```

Derivatives:

```
In[3]:=  $\partial_x (\text{Sin}[x] \text{Exp}[x])$   
(* function definition*)  
a[x_] := D[Sin[x] * Exp[x], x]
```

```
Out[3]:=  $e^x \text{Cos}[x] + e^x \text{Sin}[x]$ 
```

```
In[5]:= b[x_, y_, z_] := Exp[x y z]  
Factor[D[{x,1},{y,2},{z,4}] b[x, y, z]]
```

```
Out[6]:=  $e^{xyz} x^3 y^2 (4 + xyz) \times (12 + 10xyz + x^2 y^2 z^2)$ 
```

Integrals:

```
In[7]:=  $\int a[x] dx$ 
```

```
Out[7]:=  $e^x \text{Sin}[x]$ 
```

```
In[8]:=  $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \text{Sin}[x^2] dx$ 
```

```
Out[8]:=  $\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}$ 
```

In[9]:= $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \text{Exp}[-x^2 - y^2] \, dy \, dx$

Out[9]= π

Equations:

In[10]:= **Solve**[$x^2 - 2 == 0$, x]

Out[10]= $\{\{x \rightarrow -\sqrt{2}\}, \{x \rightarrow \sqrt{2}\}\}$

In[11]:= **FullSimplify**[**DSolve**[(y')'[t] - y[t] == **Exp**[t], y[t], t]]

Out[11]= $\{\{y[t] \rightarrow e^t \left(-\frac{1}{4} + \frac{t}{2} + c_1\right) + e^{-t} c_2\}\}$

Total time (in seconds) for the section:

In[12]:= **AbsoluteTime**[] - **timing**

Out[12]= 1.0164507

Algebra

In[13]:= (* A good first step is always to clear
all the variables in order to start from scratch*)
ClearAll["Global`*"]

In[14]:= **timing** = **AbsoluteTime**[];

In[15]:= **A** = {{**a1**, **a2**}, {**a3**, **a4**}};
B = {{**b1**, **b2**}, {**b3**, **b4**}};
MatrixForm[**A**]
MatrixForm[**B**]

Out[17]//**MatrixForm**=

$$\begin{pmatrix} a1 & a2 \\ a3 & a4 \end{pmatrix}$$

Out[18]//**MatrixForm**=

$$\begin{pmatrix} b1 & b2 \\ b3 & b4 \end{pmatrix}$$

Inverse:

In[19]:= **MatrixForm**[**Inverse**[**A**]]

Out[19]//**MatrixForm**=

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{a4}{-a2 a3 + a1 a4} & -\frac{a2}{-a2 a3 + a1 a4} \\ -\frac{a3}{-a2 a3 + a1 a4} & \frac{a1}{-a2 a3 + a1 a4} \end{pmatrix}$$

Matrix product:

In[20]:= **MatrixForm[A.B]**

Out[20]//MatrixForm=

$$\begin{pmatrix} a1 b1 + a2 b3 & a1 b2 + a2 b4 \\ a3 b1 + a4 b3 & a3 b2 + a4 b4 \end{pmatrix}$$

Transpose:

In[21]:= **MatrixForm[Transpose[A]]**

Out[21]//MatrixForm=

$$\begin{pmatrix} a1 & a3 \\ a2 & a4 \end{pmatrix}$$

Determinant:

In[22]:= **Det[A]**

Out[22]= - a2 a3 + a1 a4

Trace:

In[23]:= **Tr[A]**

Out[23]= a1 + a4

Total time (in seconds) for the section:

In[24]:= **AbsoluteTime[] - timing**

Out[24]= 0.0944131

GR computations

In[25]:= **(* A good first step is always to clear
all the variables in order to start from scratch*)
ClearAll["Global`*"]**

We are using https://doi.org/10.1142/9789812791238_0022 as a reference for this code.

In[26]:= **<< EDCRGTCcode.m**

Conventions:

1. The letters 'U' (=Up) and 'd' (=down) to denote each free tensor index
2. Finally, covariant differentiations can be denoted by preceding the differentiation index with the letter 'j' (resembling ';')
3. Contractions can be denoted by replacing the contracted indices by the same letter (Upper and lower case) while the symbol '\$' can be used to separate different tensors

Simplifying rules

In[1]:=

simpRules = TrigRules

Out[1]=

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} &\text{Cos}[h_]^2 x_ + x_ \text{Sin}[h_]^2 \rightarrow x, \text{Cot}[h_]^2 x_ + \text{Csc}[h_]^2 y_ \rightarrow y /; x + y === 0, \\ &(\text{Cot}[h_] - \text{Csc}[h_]) (\text{Cot}[h_] + \text{Csc}[h_]) \rightarrow -1 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Inserting coordinates:

Poincaré patch for AdS₂

In[2]:=

xIN = {t, z}

Out[2]=

{t, z}

Giving the metric tensor:

In[3]:=

gIN = DiagonalMatrix[{1/z^2, 1/z^2}]

Out[3]=

$$\left\{ \left\{ \frac{1}{z^2}, 0 \right\}, \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{z^2} \right\} \right\}$$

Evaluating geometric quantities:

In[4]:=

RGtensors[gIN, xIN]

$$g_{dd} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{z^2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{z^2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\text{LineElement} = \frac{d[t]^2}{z^2} + \frac{d[z]^2}{z^2}$$

$$g_{UU} = \begin{pmatrix} z^2 & 0 \\ 0 & z^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

g_{UU} computed in 0. sec

Gamma computed in 0. sec

Riemann(ddd) computed in 0. sec

Riemann(Uddd) computed in 0. sec

Ricci computed in 0. sec

Weyl computed in 0. sec

Conformally Flat

Einstein computed in 0. sec

Einstein Space**Space of Constant Curvature!**

All tasks completed in 0. seconds

Christoffel symbols:

In[5]:=

GUddOut[5]= $\left\{ \left\{ \left\{ \theta, -\frac{1}{z} \right\}, \left\{ -\frac{1}{z}, \theta \right\} \right\}, \left\{ \left\{ \frac{1}{z}, \theta \right\}, \left\{ \theta, -\frac{1}{z} \right\} \right\} \right\}$

Reimann Tensor:

In[6]:=

RUdddOut[6]= $\left\{ \left\{ \left\{ \left\{ \theta, \theta \right\}, \left\{ \theta, \theta \right\} \right\}, \left\{ \left\{ \theta, -\frac{1}{z^2} \right\}, \left\{ \frac{1}{z^2}, \theta \right\} \right\} \right\}, \left\{ \left\{ \left\{ \theta, \frac{1}{z^2} \right\}, \left\{ -\frac{1}{z^2}, \theta \right\} \right\}, \left\{ \left\{ \theta, \theta \right\}, \left\{ \theta, \theta \right\} \right\} \right\} \right\}$

Ricci tensor:

In[7]:=

RddOut[7]= $\left\{ \left\{ -\frac{1}{z^2}, \theta \right\}, \left\{ \theta, -\frac{1}{z^2} \right\} \right\}$

Ricci scalar:

In[8]:=

R

Out[8]= -2

Einstein tensor:

In[9]:=

EUdOut[9]= $\left\{ \left\{ \theta, \theta \right\}, \left\{ \theta, \theta \right\} \right\}$

Evaluating tangent vector and normal vector:

In[10]:=

TU = {t', z'}
Lower[TU, 1]Out[10]= $\{t', z'\}$

Out[11]=

 $\left\{ \frac{t'}{z^2}, \frac{z'}{z^2} \right\}$

In[12]:=

Clear[nd, nU]
nU = {nt, nz}
nd = Lower[nU, 1]Out[13]= $\{nt, nz\}$

Out[14]=

 $\left\{ \frac{nt}{z^2}, \frac{nz}{z^2} \right\}$

Normalising the normal vector:

$$T^\mu n_\mu = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad n^\mu n_\mu = 1$$

In[15]:=

```
nsolvedU = Solve[multiDot[TU, nd, {1, 1}] == 0 && Dot[nU, nd] == 1, {nt, nz}]
```

Out[15]=

$$\left\{ \left\{ nt \rightarrow -\frac{z z'}{\sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}}, nz \rightarrow \frac{z t'}{\sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}} \right\}, \right. \\ \left. \left\{ nt \rightarrow \frac{z z'}{\sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}}, nz \rightarrow -\frac{z t'}{\sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}} \right\} \right\}$$

In[16]:=

```
nU = nU /. nsolvedU[[2]]
nd = Lower[nU, 1]
```

Out[16]=

$$\left\{ \frac{z z'}{\sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}}, -\frac{z t'}{\sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}} \right\}$$

Out[17]=

$$\left\{ \frac{z'}{z \sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}}, -\frac{t'}{z \sqrt{(t')^2 + (z')^2}} \right\}$$

Stress-energy tensor:

In[18]:=

```
TphiDD =
(covD[covD[phi[t, z]]] - gdd covDiv[Raise[covD[phi[t, z]], 1], {1}] + gdd phi[t, z]) //
Simplify
```

Out[18]=

$$\left\{ \left\{ \frac{\phi[t, z] - z (\phi^{(0,1)}[t, z] + z \phi^{(0,2)}[t, z])}{z^2}, \frac{\phi^{(1,0)}[t, z]}{z} + \phi^{(1,1)}[t, z] \right\}, \right. \\ \left. \left\{ \frac{\phi^{(1,0)}[t, z]}{z} + \phi^{(1,1)}[t, z], \frac{\phi[t, z] + z (\phi^{(0,1)}[t, z] - z \phi^{(2,0)}[t, z])}{z^2} \right\} \right\}$$

Checking Maldacena's solution:

In[19]:=

$$\phi\theta[t_, z_] := \frac{\alpha + \gamma t + \delta (t^2 + z^2)}{z}$$

In[20]:=

```
covD[covD[phitheta[t, z]]] -
gdd covDiv[Raise[covD[phitheta[t, z]], 1], {1}] + gdd phitheta[t, z] // Simplify
```

Out[20]=

$$\{\{\theta, \theta\}, \{\theta, \theta\}\}$$

Induced metric:

In[21]:=

```
hdd = ReplaceAll[multiDot[multiDot[gdd, TU, {1, 1}], TU, {1, 1}],
{z -> z[u], t -> t[u], z' -> z'[u], t' -> t'[u]}]
```

Out[21]=

$$\frac{t'[u]^2 + z'[u]^2}{z[u]^2}$$

Additional

Extrinsic curvature with proper time on the boundary “u”:

```
In[22]:= (*Covariant derivative in T direction*)
covDT[x_] := D[ReplaceAll[x, {z -> z[u], t -> t[u], z' -> z'[u], t' -> t'[u]}], u] -
  ReplaceAll[multiDot[multiDot[GUdd, x, {1, 1}], TU, {1, 1}],
    {z -> z[u], t -> t[u], z' -> z'[u], t' -> t'[u]}]
```

$$K = - \frac{T^v}{T^2} \nabla_T n_v$$

```
In[23]:= K = Dot[ReplaceAll[TU / Dot[TU, Lower[TU, 1]], {z -> z[u], t -> t[u],
  z' -> z'[u], t' -> t'[u]}], covDT[nd]] // FullSimplify // Factor
```

```
Out[23]=
```

$$\frac{t'[u]^3 + t'[u] z'[u]^2 - z[u] z'[u] t''[u] + z[u] t'[u] z''[u]}{(t'[u]^2 + z'[u]^2)^{3/2}}$$

$z(u) = a t'(u)$ with $a \rightarrow 0$:

```
In[24]:= Kapprox =
  Simplify[ReplaceAll[K, {z[u] -> a t'[u], z'[u] -> a t''[u], z''[u] -> a t'''[u]}]]
```

```
Out[24]=
```

$$\frac{t'[u]^2 (t'[u] + a^2 t^{(3)}[u])}{(t'[u]^2 + a^2 t''[u]^2)^{3/2}}$$

picking up the order of approximation “o”:

```
In[25]:= L[a_] := Kapprox
(*Fixing the order of approximation *)
o = 2
L = Simplify[Series[L[a], {a, 0, o}], t'[u] > 0]
```

```
Out[26]=
```

```
Out[27]=
```

$$1 + \frac{(-3 t''[u]^2 + 2 t'[u] t^{(3)}[u]) a^2}{2 t'[u]^2} + O[a]^3$$

Action:

$\phi_r(u)$ scalar field at the boundary (Note: $\frac{1}{8\pi G}$ is to be added in order to make dimensional sense)

```
In[28]:= S = Integrate[Simplify[-(L - 1) / a^o] * phi_r[u], u]
```

```
Out[28]=
```

$$\frac{1}{2} \int \frac{\phi_r[u] (3 t''[u]^2 - 2 t'[u] t^{(3)}[u])}{t'[u]^2} du$$

```
In[29]:= rept = FuncRepRules[t[u], t0[u] + delta t[u]];
```

In[30]=

$$\text{Series}\left[\text{Simplify}\left[\text{Normal}\left[\text{Simplify}\left[-\frac{L-1}{a^0}\right]\right]\right], \{\delta t[u], 0, 0\}\right]$$

Out[30]=

$$\frac{3 (t\theta''[u] + \delta t''[u])^2 - 2 (t\theta'[u] + \delta t'[u]) t^{(3)}[u]}{2 (t\theta'[u] + \delta t'[u])^2}$$

Schwarzian properties:

In[31]=

$$\text{Sch}[x_] := \frac{\partial_{\{x,3\}} \#1}{\partial_{\{x,1\}} \#1} - \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial_{\{x,2\}} \#1}{\partial_{\{x,1\}} \#1} \right)^2 \&$$

After a Möbius transformation the Schwarzian remains the same and the Schwarzian of a Möbius transformation is identically zero

In[32]=

$$\text{Mobius}[x_] := \frac{a * x + b}{c * x + dd}$$

In[33]=

$$\text{Factor}[\text{Sch}[u][\text{Mobius}[t[u]]]] == \text{Factor}[\text{Sch}[u][t[u]]]$$

Out[33]=

True

In[34]=

$$\text{Factor}[\text{Sch}[u][\text{Mobius}[u]]]$$

Out[34]=

0